

Influence of Mass Media on Mental Health Awareness

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of the media on mental health awareness. The study further explores audience reception of mental health awareness campaigns, revealing that factors such as education, cultural beliefs, language and credibility of message sources significantly influence how people respond to mental health messages. It also highlights that while simplified communication and use of local languages improve understanding, deep-rooted cultural interpretations of mental illness continue to limit effective acceptance of mental health information. Findings indicated that the media plays a significant role in shaping public understanding by simplifying mental health concepts and encouraging dialogue on emotional and psychological well-being. However, the study also notes that limited coverage and persistent misinformation contribute to stigma, misconceptions, and reluctance to seek professional help. The study concludes that although the media is a vital tool for mental health awareness in Nigeria, its effectiveness depends on improved consistency, accuracy, and cultural sensitivity in communication.

Keywords: Mental Health Awareness; Mass Media; Public Perception; Mental Illness; Stigma; Health Communication; Audience Reception, Nigeria

Introduction

Mental health is an important part of a person's well-being, but in Nigeria, it does not get enough attention. Cases of mental health problems like depression and anxiety are increasing, yet many Nigerians do not fully understand these issues. Gureje, Lasebikan, Kola & Makanjuola (2015) state that about one in every four people in Nigeria may face a mental health challenge during their lifetime. Still, these issues are not usually talked about in the media. The media has a strong influence on how people think and can either help people learn more about mental health or continue to keep them in the dark. As a result of this, it is important to examine how the Nigerian media covers mental health, as this coverage can directly affect public attitudes and acceptance of those living with mental health conditions.

The National Health Service (NHS, 2023) describes mental health as how an individual feels, thinks, and behaves. It includes their emotional well-being, how they deal with life's ups and downs, cope with stress and make choices. Good mental health helps us to manage relationships, stay active in our communities and live our daily lives in a balanced way. Better Health Channel (2022) asserts that mental health is the way we

think and feel about ourselves and the world around us. It includes how we handle pressure, make decisions, and relate to others. Mental health does not mean always being happy, but it means being able to manage difficult emotions, recover from setbacks, and enjoy life. As noted by the author, the media plays an important role in shaping how people understand this. When the media shares positive and truthful reports about mental health, it helps people build better attitudes and reduce shame.

McCombs & Shaw (1972) in Asemah (2011) explain that the media can decide what people pay attention to by choosing which topics to talk about. This is called the "agenda-setting" role. When the media talks about mental health, it helps people learn more and show care for those who are affected. But if the media gives little or unfair attention to mental health, people stay confused or get the wrong ideas. This can make the shame and negative attitudes around mental health even worse. According to Chibueze (2020), many people in Nigeria still believe that mental health problems are caused by evil spirits, curses, or other supernatural forces, rather than understanding them as real medical conditions. These wrong beliefs make it hard for people to accept that mental health issues can be treated with proper care and support. The media also plays a part in this problem by not always showing mental health in the right way. When the media repeats these cultural beliefs and fails to correct them, it adds to the confusion and fear. This situation makes many people feel ashamed or afraid to talk about their struggles.

Mindframe (2023) points out that around the world, the way the media talks about mental health have improved over time. Many countries now follow special guidelines to help reporters share mental health stories in a more careful and respectful way. International bodies like the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Mindframe National Media Initiative have created rules to guide journalists when reporting on mental health. These rules ask reporters to use kind, truthful language and avoid using hurtful words or making mental illness seem scary or shocking. This is because using negative or dramatic language in the media can make people with mental health conditions feel judged or left out, and it can even lead others to treat them unfairly. These changes in how mental health is reported show that many media organisations across the world are trying to break down the shame around mental health and help the public understand it better. Ojebode & Adegbola (2018) say that in Nigeria, mental health issues are not frequently addressed in the media. Most of the news on health focuses on diseases like malaria and other physical sicknesses, while mental health only gets mentioned sometimes. As a result of this, people don't talk about it enough, and the government doesn't do much to improve mental health care. This makes it harder to raise awareness and push for better mental health support in the country.

From these, it can be deduced that the way the media talks about mental health is very important. When the media shares stories in a kind and honest way, it helps people understand mental health better. In countries where the media follows good rules for talking about mental health, people are usually more caring and less judgemental. This means that the media can help change bad attitudes by giving true and respectful

information. In Nigeria, if the media speaks about mental health in a better way, it can help reduce stigma and make people more willing to support those who are struggling. It is clear that the media plays an important role in shaping how the public understands and feels about mental health. Petersen *et al* (2011), in a study from South Africa, found that when the media paid more attention to mental health topics, people became more informed and were more likely to support policies that improve mental health care. They pointed out that media coverage can bring positive changes by raising awareness and pushing for better support systems. Although this seems to apply in other places, there is still little research on how the Nigerian Media covers mental health. Looking into how Nigerian media report on mental health can help uncover how the audiences view these reports, what is missing and how the media handles such sensitive matters. Therefore, this research focuses on the influence of the media on mental health awareness

In the absence of adequate media coverage, misconceptions and false beliefs about mental illness continue to persist. Many people still associate mental health conditions with spiritual attacks, curses, or supernatural forces rather than recognising them as medical conditions. These perceptions are often reinforced by certain media portrayals and societal narratives. Gureje *et al* (2015) observe that negative attitudes and beliefs about mental illness remain widespread in Nigeria and contribute significantly to stigma and discrimination. Furthermore, when mental health issues are not regularly discussed in clear, accurate, and relatable ways across media platforms, stigma within society is further strengthened. Limited or inaccurate reporting may lead individuals to feel ashamed or fearful of seeking help, thereby discouraging early intervention and professional treatment. To sum it up, insufficient media engagement with mental health issues contributes to the persistence of misunderstanding and the social exclusion of affected individuals.

Mental Health Awareness Campaign

The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2018) defines mental health awareness campaign as the process of understanding and recognising the importance of mental wellbeing. It involves knowing the signs of mental illness, supporting people who are affected, and encouraging open conversations about emotional health. Healthy People (2007) describe mental health awareness campaigns as communication strategies used to educate the public about mental health issues and to influence individuals, communities, and government decisions in ways that support better mental well-being. These campaigns involve sharing updates and information about mental health through the media and other platforms to help people understand the topic better. They also include using reporting techniques to cover mental health topics, such as writing detailed reports, creating features, or investigating mental health-related cases. The goal is to raise awareness, reduce stigma, and encourage people to take mental health seriously and seek help when needed.

Mental health awareness campaigns are a specialised area of communication that involve sharing key details such as who is affected, what the issue is, when and where it

happens, why it matters, and how it can be addressed about mental health issues and trends. It is a challenging task because mental health, like other areas of medicine, can be quite complex. As Gibbs & Warehove (2002) explain, mental health professionals use terms that are hard for the general public to understand. This means that those who create mental health messages whether journalists, campaigners, or media houses must first understand what experts or research articles are saying, and then explain it in clear, simple language so that everyone, including those with little or no medical background, can understand and benefit from the information. Jorm (2012) notes that increased awareness leads to improved mental health literacy and better attitudes towards those affected. Mental health awareness helps to reduce ignorance and fear surrounding mental illness. Many people are unaware of what mental health conditions are, how they affect individuals, and what support is available. Awareness campaigns are therefore important in providing correct information, breaking down myths, and promoting early diagnosis and treatment.

Role of the Mass Media in Promoting Mental Health Awareness in Nigeria

According to Asemah (2019), the media has changed the way people communicate, connect, and share information. While it provides many benefits, it also brings concerns about its effects on mental health and well-being. Agba (2012) points out that the mass media is an important source of mental health information, resources, and support for many people. Those dealing with mental health challenges can listen to or watch programmes that share personal stories, provide understanding, and offer advice from experts or others who have experienced similar difficulties. This kind of access helps people feel empowered and encourages them to seek the help and support they need.

Chandrasena & Illankon (2022) say that the media gives people an easy way to connect with others who share similar experiences, which can help improve their mental health. When people watch programmes that mirror what they are going through, they feel accepted and part of a group. Over time, this feeling of belonging can make them feel valued and connected to others. The authors also explain that the media helps people keep and strengthen their existing relationships by showing information that can start important conversations. Wap (2020) highlights that the media plays a key role in spreading awareness about mental health, reducing stigma, and challenging stereotypes. News paper publications, radio and television shows, documentaries, and adverts can reach many people, share useful information, and encourage open talks about mental health in a way that is easy to understand.

Furthermore, media campaigns play an important role in supporting efforts to improve mental health services, policies, and resources. These campaigns can encourage people to back causes like more funding for mental health programmes, better access to care, and anti-stigma activities by raising awareness. Vinaj (2017,) also points out that irrespective of its benefits, the media can affect mental health negatively. The author warns that if the negative impacts the media are not noticed and dealt with, they could seriously harm the mental and social well-being of young people.

Influence of the Media on Public Understanding of Mental Health Issues

As described by Singhal & Rogers (2003), the media serves as an effective platform for promoting health because it appeals to both emotions and reasoning. It has long been one of the most powerful tools for spreading information to the public. With its wide reach, the media plays a major role in educating people about mental health issues. Wakefield, Barbara & Hornik (2010) state that one major advantage of the media is its ability to improve public understanding of mental health by presenting information in a simple and easy-to-understand manner. Mental health issues can sometimes be difficult to discuss because of the complex medical terms and explanations often used by professionals. However, the media helps simplify these concepts. Through different forms of media content such as news reports, interviews, talk shows, documentaries, social media content, and drama programmes, mental health information can be explained in ways that ordinary people can easily understand. As noted by Wakefield *et al*

A short news report on TV about depression can talk about what it feels like, what causes it, and how someone can get help. This can be done in just a few minutes using simple words, real-life stories, and pictures to help people relate. When people see someone like them talking about their mental health on TV, it helps them feel less alone and more willing to talk about their own problems. TV can help reduce fear and confusion around mental health by showing that it is normal and can happen to anyone. It can teach people that having a mental illness doesn't mean someone is weak or dangerous. Instead, it shows that help is available and recovery is possible. This kind of clear and friendly communication on television can help change how people think and feel about mental health in a good way.

Nwachukwu & Ezeh (2017) argue that in many developing countries, where access to the internet is still limited and unreliable, media platforms have remained one of the main ways people get information about health. This is mostly true in rural areas who are unable to afford smartphones and data. In Nigeria, radio and television stations play an important role in educating the public about mental health. These stations reach a wide audience, including people in villages and towns, and are trusted sources of information in many homes. Nwabueze (2015) assert that mental health campaigns through the mass media are very common during awareness events like World Mental Health Day and during public health emergencies when stress and anxiety are high. Through these campaigns, the media can help explain mental health conditions such as depression, anxiety, and bipolar disorder in a simple and clear way. Media campaigns help teach people how to recognise signs of mental distress, where to find help, and how to support others who may be struggling.

Audience Reception of Mental Health Awareness Campaigns

Mass Communication scholars such as Gureje *et al* (2006) explain that audience reception refers to the way people receive, interpret and respond to messages presented

by the media. It is important because the success of a campaign depends on how well the audience accepts and applies the information provided. Many factors influence audience reception, including culture, education, personal experience, and the method through which messages are delivered. According to the authors, cultural beliefs and stigma play a major role in how people respond to mental health campaigns. In many parts of Nigeria and other developing countries, mental illness is often misunderstood. Some individuals believe that mental health problems are signs of weakness or are caused by supernatural forces. This stigma prevents many people from accepting media campaign messages and seeking professional help.

Jorm (2012) states that education and literacy levels also influence how audiences receive mental health campaigns through the media. People with higher levels of education are more likely to understand mental health information and may be more willing to change their attitudes toward mental illness. However, individuals with low literacy levels may struggle to understand medical terms and complex explanations. As a result, they may reject the messages because they do not fully trust or understand them. Therefore, there is a need for media campaigns to use simple and clear language to reach audiences effectively.

The credibility of the person or organisation sharing the message is another important factor that influences audience reception. When media campaigns involve respected professionals such as doctors, community leaders, or popular media personalities, audiences are more likely to pay attention and believe the information being presented. People often trust messages that come from familiar and respected individuals because they believe such sources possess knowledge and good intentions. For example, when a medical expert or a popular broadcaster discusses mental health issues through the media, audiences are more likely to take the message seriously and follow the advice provided. This trust increases the effectiveness of the campaign and encourages more people to understand mental health issues and seek help when necessary (Noar *et al* 2009).

Similarly, Nwosu & Uche (2018) assert that the language used in media messages affects how audiences understand mental health campaigns. The use of clear and simple language makes it easier for people, regardless of their educational background, to understand the information being communicated. Mental health messages presented in local languages or Pidgin English are often more relatable and understandable to many Nigerians. This is important because the use of complicated medical terms may confuse audiences and reduce their interest in the message. When people do not understand the information being shared through the media, they are less likely to pay attention to it or take it seriously.

Counter-Argument

Some concerns have been raised regarding the extent to which the media effectively promotes mental health awareness in Nigeria. While the media is recognised as a source of information, education, and support on mental health issues, critics argue that its role

is not always consistently positive or reliable. In many cases, mental health content shared through radio, television, newspapers, documentaries, interviews, and social media may lack proper regulation, leading to the circulation of misleading or unverified information. This is particularly concerning among young people who are more exposed to social media platforms where harmful or inaccurate content can easily influence perceptions of mental health.

Furthermore, audience reception of mental health awareness campaigns is not uniform, as several factors limit how people respond to such messages. These include differences in educational background, cultural beliefs, personal experiences, credibility of message sources, and language barriers. Although simplified language, local languages, and Pidgin English have been used to improve understanding, many individuals still struggle to fully engage with mental health messages due to deep-rooted cultural and religious interpretations of mental illness. In many communities, mental health conditions are still associated with spiritual causes or personal weakness, which reduces acceptance of medical explanations and discourages affected individuals from seeking professional help. Additionally, distrust in media messages and the perceived credibility of those delivering the information can significantly weaken the impact of awareness campaigns.

That aside, while the media has contributed to shaping public understanding of mental health issues, its influence is not evenly distributed across Nigeria. People in rural areas often have limited access to consistent and high-quality media content, which reduces the reach and effectiveness of mental health awareness campaigns. Even in more connected areas, some media platforms tend to prioritise entertainment or sensational content over in-depth health education, which can limit the depth of public understanding. There is also concern that continuous exposure to distressing and poorly presented mental health content may negatively affect the emotional well-being of vulnerable individuals.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the Nigerian media has not given sufficient and consistent attention to mental health issues, despite the growing prevalence of mental health challenges in society. The dominance of topics such as politics, crime, and the economy in media reporting has resulted in limited coverage of mental health awareness. This has contributed to gaps in public knowledge, where many individuals remain uninformed about the causes, symptoms, and treatment options for mental health conditions.

The study also concludes that inadequate media coverage has allowed misconceptions and negative beliefs about mental illness to persist. In many cases, mental health conditions are still wrongly associated with spiritual or supernatural causes, which continues to reinforce stigma and discrimination. Furthermore, the lack of regular, clear, and accurate mental health communication in the media discourages affected individuals from seeking help, thereby worsening social exclusion and delaying treatments.

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